

MODELLING THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF WRINKLED COMPOSITES FROM NDT DATA

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ABSTRACT

Wrinkles are a common phenomenon during the composite manufacturing stage and have a significant influence on mechanical properties. Recent development in 3D-characterisation techniques using non-destructive testing (NDT) methods, such as ultrasonics and X-ray computed tomography, have made it possible to capture the detailed internal features of composite structures. After the inversion process to determine quantitative profiles of material properties such as fibre-tow orientations, finite element models can be created by a transfer process in order to predict how these wrinkles will affect the mechanical performance. The work presented in this paper is aimed at developing a methodology to transfer the material-property data sets containing out-of-plane wrinkle information into an FE model in a format that can be interpreted by ABAQUS 6.12 so that it can run the model to assess the mechanical performance. In order to confirm the reliance of the transfer process, a comparison between predicted results and experimental observations is made.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have an increasing usage in a wide range of applications, from advanced sport components to the aircraft industry [1], due to its superior performance, particularly of its high stiffness and low weight. However, some kinds of defects may be induced during the manufacturing stage of composites. Common defects are fibre waviness (in-plane and out-of-plane), inclusions and porosity [1]. In terms of the waviness, the causal factors are complex and varied and may include the volume contraction due to chemical or thermal shrinkage [2], the mismatched size between components and mould [3] or consolidation proving excess length of material [4]. Van Dreumel and Kamp showed that the mechanical performance of tensile strength will suffer about 20% decrease due to the existence of out-of-plane wrinkles [5], while Bloom et al [3] demonstrated that the tensile strength would lose up to 40% when 30° maximum-angle misalignment wrinkles exist in the structure. For compression loading, 36% reduction of compression strength was detected in composites with wrinkles of amplitude approximately 1.5 time the ply thicknesses [6]. Mukhopadhyay et al [7] obtained similar reduction of compression strength at 33% due to 12° (maximum angle) out-of-plane wrinkles. Hence it is important to understand how wrinkles will influence the mechanical performance when determining acceptance criteria for wrinkling.

With the development of 3D-characterisation methods in non-destructive testing (NDT), it is now realistic to capture and map the internal detailed features of composite structures. Ultrasonics and X-ray tomography (CT) [8-10] are the two most widely used methods to achieve this characterisation process. Rokhlin and Wang [11] reconstructed the laminar and bulk elastic properties based on double-through-transmission ultrasound technique and Hasiotis et al [12] observed the shape and position of manufactured defects in CFRP coupons by using ultrasonics. Moreover, Balasubramaniam and Rao [13] determined the stiffness matrix of composites by inverting the incident ultrasonic bulk wave data based on genetic algorithms. In terms of the application of X-ray tomography, Babout et al [14] applied this to monitor the whole damage process, from the initiation to the final complete failure and created 3D images to reconstruct the deformed process of cavities. However, the above published research is just related to the reconstruction of damage processes, not fully obtaining the 3D characterisation to capture the detailed internal features. Landis and Keane [15] successfully achieved

3D characterisation of microstructures based on X-ray CT images, but their work was not focused on composite materials. Considering the specific features of composites, it is crucial to accurately capture and map 3D fibre orientations in order to obtain the 3D characterisation. Nelson and Smith [16] are concentrating on this inversion process from ultrasonic full-waveform data to form material-property data sets. The work presented in this paper is the logical following step based on their achievement.

In order to obtain a better assessment of how wrinkles influence the mechanical performance, appropriate failure mechanisms need to be incorporated in the models, and failure criteria applied. The work done by Bloom et al [3] implied that the accuracy of failure stress predicted by 3D FE models is obviously influenced by the accuracy of wrinkle geometry simulated in the model. Makeev et al [17] developed models with nonlinear shear stress-strain response and experiments containing wrinkles; they showed that failure was initiated by wrinkles and damage was more severe in the wrinkled regions. In the models presented in this paper the damage mechanism of delamination is simulated by cohesive elements at the ply interfaces which are available in ABAQUS/explicit, whilst matrix-crack and fibre-kink failure mechanisms are modelled by user-defined subroutines from Mukhopadhyay et al [7], based on original work by Pinho [18, 19].

The work presented in this paper is focused on the effects of out-of-plane wrinkles and uses material-property maps from inversion of NDT data to create finite-element models. The NDT data is from ultrasonic and X-ray CT scans and contains internal details of the structure, including the variation of fibre orientations and ply thicknesses [16]. Matlab-based scripts have been created to transfer these material-property maps into models and store them in files that are interpreted and run by ABAQUS to assess mechanical performance. Relevant parameters for each element, such as the stiffness-axes orientation, are calculated by the Matlab scripts simultaneously. Section 2 is the discussion of the models created by this transfer process; material-property maps were created either by inverting real NDT data sets or by simulation from photographic evidence of the edge of the wrinkled coupons, with assumptions about the consistency of the wrinkle geometry beyond the exposed edge. This is followed by the validation of the transfer process for compression loading by comparison of predicted results with experimental observations in section 3.

2 FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING TRANSFER PROCESS

2.1 The transfer process

Matlab-based scripts were developed to transfer material-property map files into models and store them in ABAQUS formats containing the relevant parameters which are used to form the finite element models in ABAQUS. The transfer process is put in context in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Flow diagram showing how the transfer process, the subject of this paper, uses the inverted NDT data to create FE models for ABAQUS to run.

In order to create the basic mesh for the model, a complete map of the depth of each ply interface is required from inverted NDT data – referred to as the Ply-interface Depth Map. Full ply-thickness hexahedral elements are used to represent plies and the positions of their eight nodes are calculated directly from the Ply-interface Depth Map. The side faces of these ply elements are on a square grid which is linked to the spacing of the original NDT data but may be on a finer grid in order to achieve acceptable representation of defects in the model. The top and bottom faces of each ply element are angled and follow the undulations of the plies as the wrinkles are tracked in the Ply-interface Depth Map. The stiffness axes within each element are oriented by the Matlab script according to an In-plane Orientation Map - also inverted from the NDT data - combined with the out-of-plane angles derived

from the Ply-interface Depth Map. These ply elements are eight-node solid elements with reduced integration algorithm (C3D8R). Between the plies, eight-node cohesive elements (COH3D8) are added at the ply interface to enable the delamination failure mechanism. The composite material used in this paper is Hexcel's IM7/8552, and the relevant properties [20] for a ply element are listed in Table 1 and properties [7, 21, 22] for a cohesive element are listed in Table 2.

E_1 [GPa]	E_2 [GPa]	E_3 [GPa]	G_{12} [GPa]	G_{13} [GPa]	G_{23} [GPa]	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}	α_{11} [$^{\circ}$ C]	α_{22} [$^{\circ}$ C]	α_{33} [$^{\circ}$ C]
161	11.38	11.38	5.17	5.17	3.98	0.32	0.32	0.436	0	3e-5	3e-5

Table 1: The ply-element properties of IM7/8552.

It is important to allow matrix cracking in plies that are not in line with the loading direction, and fibre-kinking in the plies with fibres in line with the load. Thus the Matlab script assigns different properties for the different plies. Parameters for modelling matrix-crack and fibre-kink failure mechanisms [7, 17, 19, 21] are shown in Table 3.

G_{IC} [N/mm]	G_{IIC} [N/mm]	K_I [MPa]	K_{II} [MPa]	σ_I^{\max} [MPa]	σ_{II}^{\max} [MPa]	α
0.26	1.002	10^5	10^5	60	90	1

Table 2: The properties for cohesive elements between plies.

Y_C [MPa]	S_L [MPa]	θ_i [degree]	G_{IC} [N/mm]	G_{IIC} [N/mm]	G_{kink} [N/mm]	α
250	120	0.97	0.26	1.002	80	1

Table 3: The properties for matrix crack and fibre kink of IM7/8552.

The parameters listed in the above tables have the following meanings: E_1 , E_2 and E_3 are the elastic modulus in three directions, G_{12} , G_{13} and G_{23} are shear modulus. ν_{12} , ν_{13} and ν_{23} refer to Poisson's ratio. The direction subscripts of 1, 2 and 3 signify the fibre direction and two transverse directions respectively. The symbol α in Table 1 is the thermal expansion coefficient. K is the elastic stiffness and σ is the damage initiation stress; the subscripts of I and II refer to pure mode I and mode II. α in Table 2 is the parameter in the power law to govern the propagation process of delamination. G_{IC} and G_{IIC} are the interlaminar critical energy release rates. Y_C and S_L are the compression strength and longitudinal shear strength respectively, based on the fibre direction. θ_i is the initial fibre misalignment angle (expected maximum angular deviation for a fibre in a pre-preg ply) in the structure. G_{kink} is the in-plane compressive fracture energy for the fibre-kink elements.

2.2 Simulated 3D-map input

Two types of model were created by the transfer process. The first (Fig. 2) was developed from the simulated material-property maps, which were obtained from a Matlab-based simulator and were determined from photographs of the edge of experimental test coupons, assuming the wrinkles are continuous through the width of the coupon. The simulator was developed to replicate the inversion process applied to NDT images but create the same format of data sets since pre-test NDT data was not available. This allows isolation of the transfer process – the subject of this paper - from the inversion process, which is beyond the scope of the paper (Fig. 1).

Figure 2: Images of fibre wrinkling in the $[45/90/-45/0]_{3S}$ test coupons from the work of Mukhopadhyay [7], (a) photograph of coupon edge (note the lighter plies are 0-degree and the darker ones are blocks of 45/90/-45 or -45/90/45), (b) from Matlab-based simulator, (c) from the FE model, the red lines in (c) illustrate the $-45^\circ/0^\circ/45^\circ$ plies.

The experimental test coupons produced by Mukhopadhyay et al [7] had been tested to failure mechanically, with high-speed photography to identify failure modes. The data from these tests was made available for the current project in order to validate the transfer process and photographs of the coupon edges were available, so the simulator was used to replicate the Ply-interface Depth Map and the In-plane Orientation Map in each case. The coupons contained 24 plies (ply sequence: $[45/90/-45/0]_{3S}$) of thickness 0.25 mm with wrinkles induced by adding extra strips in the 90-degree plies. This had the effect of creating four-interface groups where each group had a different geometry and the middle group had a double-ply of 0 degrees at the mid-plane. In the simulated model, the wrinkle was a Gaussian-enveloped cosine wrinkle in the middle area, and the highest severity wrinkle was located in the group of plies surrounding the mid-plane. The adjacent four-interface groups had reducing amplitudes of wrinkle in the ratio 0.63 : 0.39 : 0.0 [7], relative to the central group (1.0). By comparison of image (a), (b) and (c) in Figure 2, it is clear that the features in the composite structure can be successfully reconstructed in the simulator and the FE models by the transfer process.

2.3 Real 3D-map input data

The transfer process was then applied to a Ply-interface Depth Map and an In-plane Orientation Map generated by inversion of real ultrasonic NDT data for a specimen with twenty-one 0.125 mm-thick plies and nominal ply sequence of $[45/0/-45/90/-45/0/45]_3$. These maps are illustrated by the images in Figure 3 where the unit vector in line with the fibres is mapped in three dimensions as a vector field and then imaged using stream lines and tubes to represent the fibre tows.

The model created from these maps was imported into ABAQUS and was run in a compressive loading scenario to produce the results shown in Figure 4. From the images in Figure 4, it can be seen that the combined in-plane and out-of-plane waviness in this specimen causes considerable variation in out-of-plane displacement U_3 and in-plane longitudinal stress S_{11} when the model is run with an in-

plane compression loading. This model indicates the generality of transfer process successfully achieving the full transfer from NDT data sets to FE models. The specimen could not be tested experimentally so NDT data must in future be acquired for experimental coupons prior to test to show if the transfer process can accurately predict mechanical performance with the influence of defects.

Figure 3: Vector field data for the unit vector parallel to the fibres, with fibre-tow ‘tubes’ illustrating the wrinkling and in-plane waviness in each ply, showing (a) 90° (red), (b) 0° (blue), (c) 45° (green) and (d) -45° (white) plies. Note the aspect ratio used exaggerates out-of-plane distances with 10x magnification. The two 45° (green) layers in the bulk of the specimen are double plies, 0.25 mm thick.

Figure 4: Out-of-plane displacement, U_3 (left) and in-plane stress, S_{11} (right) under in-plane compression for an FE model created from real NDT data of a 21-ply specimen of stacking sequence $[45/0/-45/90/-45/0/45]_3$.

3 VALIDATION OF THE TRANSFER PROCESS

3.1 Experimental validation

The validation presented is for out-of-plane wrinkles under compressive loading. Three severities of wrinkle were investigated with maximum angles of 6°, 10° and 12°. The experimental coupons were manufactured and tested by Mukhopadhyay et al [7] with Ply-interface Depth Maps and In-plane Orientation Maps simulated as described in Section 2.2. Validation was performed with three failure mechanisms in the transfer process: delamination, matrix cracking and fibre kinking.

3.2 Mean wrinkle severity models

Comparisons of experimental tests with predictions based on a measured average wrinkle severity across all coupons extracted from a single panel are listed in Table 4. The models gave predictions for the compressive failure stresses that overestimated by less than one standard deviation of the experimental mean for 6° and 10° severities. But for 12° maximum wrinkle angle, the discrepancy is an underestimate of nearly two standard deviations. This greater discrepancy for the 12° coupons may be because the model was based on a perfectly shaped, symmetrical 12° wrinkle, whereas the real coupons had slightly different angles on the each side of the specimen.

Wrinkle levels - Maximum angle		6°	10°	12°
Mean wrinkle severity models value	MPa	534	444	379
Experimental mean value	MPa	528	428	432
Experimental Standard Deviation	MPa	28	21	30
CV	%	5.2	4.9	6.9

Table 4: The compressive failure stress for each severity wrinkles from models and experiments.

When comparing the predicted and experimental damage distributions (Fig. 5), the experimental delamination failure was initiated near the highest-angle region, for all models and experiments. Matrix cracking and fibre kinking failures occurred in similar regions for the models as observed in the experiments. The level of agreement and similar distribution of damage between the models and experimental results implies that the transfer process is validated up to 10° for prediction of compressive performance using FE models with appropriated damage criteria, but further refinements may be needed for the larger angles.

Figure 5: Damage distribution of 12° coupon: (a) photograph of initial coupon failure, (b) delamination prediction, (c) matrix-cracking and fibre-kinking failure prediction.

3.3 Coupon-specific wrinkle severity models

Deviations from ‘perfectly shaped’ wrinkles and variations in wrinkle severity existed across the manufactured panels and from coupon to coupon. NDT methods offer an opportunity for identifying these variations, and applying the transfer process to a more precisely defined local wrinkle shape and severity, allowing investigation of the influence on mechanical performance of these local factors. During this second confirmation stage, the aim was to validate that the local variance in the structure can be captured and transferred into models specific to each coupon, thus investigating the influence on failure stress of characterising local features with NDT. Again, models with three failure mechanisms as described above were created by the scripts for each severity-level of wrinkles. Simulations of the Ply-interface Depth Maps and In-plane Orientation Maps were again used, but the simulations were specific to each coupon tested. For each severity level, a single panel had been cut

into eight coupons for experimental testing. Three coupons (two edge coupons and one from the middle) were chosen as the basis of the coupon specific FE models and photographs of the edges were analysed in detail in order to create coupon-specific simulations, but they were still the best-fit symmetrical Gaussian-envelope cosine waves, as described above.

The results are expressed in Figure 6 where it is significant that the agreement between model predictions and experimental failure stresses are smallest for coupons cut from the middle region of the manufactured panel at each level wrinkle case, while the largest difference is shown in the 8th test coupon for each severity-level of wrinkles. This regularity is probably from the manufacturing process, although the wrinkle severity should be at the same level through the width of the panel and be uniform for all eight test coupons at each level wrinkle experiments, minor variations in wrinkle severity are quite possible during the layup procedure, especially near the two edges. The trend in the figure (Fig. 6) has well indicated this. The difference in the edge-coupon cases is probably due to the existence of minor factors which are located near the edges, rather than just statistical variance of the wrinkles. This will be investigated further during the next stage of this work. The models in this section confirm that the minor details in the internal structure do affect the mechanical performance as what we expect. It also implies that when the transfer process is used for the assessment of mechanical performance, it is helpful in creating models with detailed features from NDT methods.

Figure 6: The failure stress from models and experiments based on single coupon. The red circles indicate the coupons from the middle of the panel. Models mean_1, 1_1, 1_5 and 1_8 had 12° wrinkles, mean_2, 2_1, 2_5 and 2_8 had 10° wrinkles, mean_3, 3_1, 3_5 and 3_8 had 6° wrinkles, Bars (blue, grey and dark blue) are from models, and orange, yellow and green bars are based on coupons. The bars named as mean_1, 2 or 3 denotes the average data for each level-wrinkle.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, Matlab-based scripts are reported to achieve the transfer process to FE models from material-property maps inverted from NDT data sets. The transfer process has been applied to both real and simulated property maps to create the FE models. The validation process has provided justification for the use of this method to predict the mechanical performance of composite structures by FE models transferred from inverted NDT data sets. Further comparison between predictions and experimental results based on single test coupon data indicates that internal coupon variations have an effect on failure stress. It is possible to model these detailed features using this transfer process based on NDT data sets. This work has so far focused on the influence of out-of-plane wrinkles; the effect of in-plane wrinkles will be investigated in future work, where it is more difficult to quantify wrinkle severity by means other than NDT. The transfer process based on real NDT data sets containing out-of-plane or in-plane wrinkles is justified by the ability to model coupon-specific wrinkling based on local accurate geometric details.

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